

Iron Age gold: Time for a shake-up?

('Iron Age Dialogues' conference, Cardiff, 30th April to 2nd May 2025.)

by Tess Machling

Introduction

Although there is an intention to publish the proceedings of the Cardiff conference, for me, publication in print will once again mean I will be facing significant image rights costs, which will not allow for the full publication of everything I said in my talk: I will need to adapt what I want to say to fit the needs of a supposedly 'commercial', printed volume (for more about the problems of how 'commercial' publication is defined, see [here](#)).

With this in mind, I thought I would share the slides and commentary of my talk here. If you are a regular visitor to [The Big Book of Torcs](#), you will be aware that I work with a team of goldsmiths, silversmiths and jewellers, and that my work comes from a craft perspective on gold: how torcs were made and what that can tell us. This talk was very much a result of this work, and argues that to ignore the craft perspective, as sadly so often happens, can cause all manner of problems with interpretation. In short, we cannot tell much about widely what an artefact means, unless we know how it was made.

So in this spirit, this is my talk: I do hope you enjoy it.

Iron Age gold: Time for a shake-up?

Gold in Iron Age Britain consists of a small suite of artefact types: thousands of coins, a few 'v'-shaped finger rings, a couple of bracelets and, apart from that, the bulk are torcs, likely made both for the arm and the neck.

Gold in Iron Age Britain.

After an apparent hiatus from the Late Bronze Age to c.300 BC, Iron Age gold work reappears in the archaeological record.

Leekfrith
© The Potteries Museum

Towton
© The Yorkshire Museum

Iron Age gold items (apart from coins) are restricted to torcs, armings and bracelets with a very few simple finger rings.

Left to right: Snettisham Grotesque torc; Clevedon torc; Witham finger ring; Snettisham arm ring.
© Trustees of the British Museum

The overwhelming majority of Iron Age gold objects are torcs...

Snettisham © Trustees of the British Museum

There is also a hiatus in gold work from the later Bronze Age to the middle Iron Age. However, almost each time a new torc/torc assemblage is found, the pattern changes: for example, the finding of the Leekfrith hoard, in 2016, put the dating of British-found gold torcs earlier by a couple of hundred years.

However, there is an absence of context...

Archaeologically excavated:

Antiquarian/detected/accidental/unpublished:

Snettisham hoards G, H, J, K, L; Blair Drummond and Hengistbury Head
 ...and Snettisham is only just published.

Alrewas, Bawsey, Caistor, Clevedon, Essendon, Glascote, Ipswich, Kings Lynn, Leekfrith, South-west Norfolk, Middleton Hall, North Creake, Netherurd, Needwood Forest, Newark, Sedgeford, Shenstone, Snettisham A, B, C, D, E, F, M, N & P, Spetisbury, Near Stowmarket, Towton, Ulceby ...etc

Often all we have is the torcs themselves
 > interpretation, dating, etc is difficult.

The majority of torcs that have been found have no context and were not excavated archaeologically. Even with the excavated torcs, several have only had the findspots excavated, *after* the torc/s have been removed. For more about this, see [here](#). As such, we have very little contextual information for torcs, which makes interpretation, dating, etc difficult.

Snettisham, East Anglia

Snettisham (with at least 300 torcs represented) is the ultimate in torc kleptomania. For whatever reason it is a collected/curated group of many types and dates of torcs which were deposited at a similar time.

3-4 torcs in a deposit is the norm. Snettisham is an anomaly!!!

Blair Drummond

Ipswich

Leekfrith

Towton

Netherurd

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We also have this huge site at Snettisham, with fourteen hoards, and hundreds of torcs which tends to dominate the narrative of Iron Age torcs. However, the normal pattern of deposition is of 3-4 torcs in a single deposit. As such, we need to bear in mind that Snettisham would seem to be an anomaly.

A craft perspective.

I look at gold from a craft perspective and the slide below summarizes some of the problems I've encountered in gold studies, and a few suggestions of how things could be improved. If you want to delve into more detail, my issues with the recent Snettisham publication have been raised [here](#).

We need to find a better way...

A craft perspective on metalwork.

- Metals, such as gold, can only be worked in certain ways and those ways will be affected by alloy composition, available technology, skill and tools: that is not a perspective, or an opinion.
- Although there are some overlaps, the tools and methods used in working one metal are very different to the tools and methods used in another. The evidence for each type of metal working and their archaeological signatures will also be very different > The terms 'metalworkers', 'metalworking' etc. are not useful descriptors.
- However, there are different techniques that can be used to achieve a similar outcome within the parameters of each metal. As such, when researching metal artefacts, a range of opinions from a group of practitioners skilled in a variety of methods will allow for the broadest width of possibilities. N.B. Western techniques and terminology may not be relevant.
- Only those with extensive skills and experience in specific metalworking techniques can offer accurate insights into the craft of the past. Experimental/experiential archaeology is really not enough.
- Research into gold working often cannot be peer-reviewed in the traditional sense. Many of the most skilled and knowledgeable goldsmiths/silversmiths and jewellers have no formal academic qualifications to allow them to do so. This leaves a void in our knowledge and learning and it leads to mistakes.
- Scientific instruments and techniques can only tell us so much and they are not a definitive method for understanding artefacts: often skill and experience combined with a good pair of magnifiers produces as valid results.
- Measurements (dimensions, thicknesses, weights, etc.) are essential and photos will never be enough: metalwork analysis needs to be carried out in person.

In short, we really cannot start talking about the bigger picture – overarching theories of manufacture, distribution, art styles etc. - unless we establish the basics of how something was made...

... and the way something was made will often give us a huge amount of relevant information!

The origins of gold.

In this next section, I want to look at Iron Age gold from a craft perspective and, via a few examples, show how current theories may not be offering accurate insights into Iron Age gold and gold-working.

The idea that Iron Age British gold is imported and recycled is long standing. For a discussion of this, please see [here](#). However, if we look at gold *sources*, this is not necessarily the case. There is a rough line running from about Weymouth to the Wash, on one side of which are found predominantly sheet work/hammered torcs and the other, predominantly cast torcs.

Could this relate to ancestral working traditions in areas where gold is found, in the north and west, and which is not seen in the south and east, which have an absence of gold sources, and where a casting technology (probably in bronze) is more traditional?

If we look at where gold is uncovered today, there is an abundance of material being found, although this material is largely unknown in the archaeological world. The examples below have been found in Scotland over only a few years, within a local area: I can't say more than that, but it is enough to say that it is a lot of gold from a very small area!

But what this shows is that gold is still abundant if you know where to look, and imagine how much more there was thousands of years ago, before the alluvial sources had been stripped out.

The finder of the gold nuggets kindly had them assayed (composition tested) for me, and the results can be seen below: not hugely different to the percentages found in several torcs. So, as [discussed in a previous blog](#), can we be certain that torcs were made from coins? or could alluvial, or indeed mined, gold be a source?

Analysis...

- Nugget B contains approximately 949‰ gold, the remainder is almost all silver
- Nugget F contains approximately 762‰ gold, the remainder is almost all silver
- Nugget A contains approx. 899‰ gold
- The approx. values for other elements present in the alloy are: 75‰ silver and 25‰ iron.
- Nugget A contains approx. 885‰ gold.
- The approx. values for other elements present in the alloy are: 103‰ silver and 10‰ iron.
- Nugget E contains approximately 853‰ gold, the remainder is almost all silver.
- Nugget H contains approximately 852‰ gold, the remainder is almost all silver.
- Samples 2 and 5 contain approximately 808‰ gold
- Sample 1 contains approximately 870‰ gold
- Sample 3 contains approximately 917‰ gold
- Samples 4 and 6 contain approximately 940‰ gold
- The remainder of all samples is almost all silver
- Nugget contains approx. 807‰ gold.
- The approx. values for other elements present in the alloy are: 162‰ silver, 9.5‰ iron.
- Traces of copper and nickel found in some areas of the nugget.
- High iron content detected (brown areas).
- Nugget A contains approx. 757‰ gold.
- The approx. values for other elements present in the alloy are: 225‰ silver, 8.5‰ iron and 9.4‰ mercury.
- Nugget A contains approximately 770‰ gold, the remainder is almost all silver and a small quantity of iron.
- Nugget D contains approximately 644‰ gold, the remainder is almost all silver.
- Nugget G contains approximately 649‰ gold, the remainder is almost all silver.

Surface compositions:

Leekfrith hoard, Staffs:
c.74-78%gold, 18-22% silver, 2-3% copper

Snettisham buffer torc:
c.80%gold, 18% silver, 3% copper

Newark, Notts:
c.67% gold, 32% silver, 1% copper

Netherurd, Peeblesshire:
c.70% gold, 25% silver, 5% copper, 0.03% iron

Caistor, Lincs:
c.72%gold, 25% silver, 3% copper

Ipswich hoard, Suffolk:
c.66-89%gold, 10-28% silver, 0.1-12% copper

Compositions range from c.95% gold, 5% silver to c.65% gold, 35 % silver...

...with various other metals (e.g copper, iron, nickel and mercury) present.

Does 'coins to torcs' (and 'torcs to coins') still hold?

Travelling torcs.

This links to a further issue in gold studies: the assumption that all gold artefacts travelled from making sites in the south to the north.

Travelling torcs, 1806 to 2024...

'The most unaccountable part of this discovery is how so many articles, apparently of different ages and purposes, should have been found all together, and in such a spot...'

Letter from John Lawton to Sir Walter Scott, 1806.

'It is certain that none of the objects composing the Shaw Hill [Netherurd] hoard originated in or anywhere near the district in which they were found. The coins are of non-British origin, but the British character of the other articles would suggest that the hoard came rather from an area of distribution in south-east Britain...'

Eacham, The 'Cairnmuir' hoard from Netherurd, Peeblesshire, 1958

'To this east-central school of Snettisham torc 'A' belongs the well-known gold torc terminal found at Cairnmuir [Netherurd], Peebles...it is here regarded as an export to the north...'

Fox, Pattern and Purpose, 1958

'Most torcs from the rest of southern Britain are of broadly the same type as those found in East Anglia...[and] almost certainly would have been connected to the same 'East Anglian' workshop, perhaps travelling north through a process of gift exchange or diplomatic ties...'

La Niece, Farley, Meeks & Joy, *Gold in Iron Age Britain*, 2018

'Indeed, two torcs which show close similarities, both to each other...and finds from East Anglia, were found much further north, suggesting they may have travelled through trade and exchange to their eventual sites of deposition.'

Joy & Farley, The Snettisham Hoards, 2024

As can be seen above, the idea that gold artefacts moved from south to north has been around for a long time. However, with no evidence of southern workshops, or indeed any workshops for working gold, can this certainty be justified?

But... not all fine metalwork originates in East Anglia...

Fig 35.3. The movement of massive metalwork. (The source of the York factor is not clear as the type cannot be allocated to a specific sub-region.)

Hunter, *Art in context: the massive metalworking tradition of north-east Scotland*, 2014

'Norfolk' © Trustees of the British Museum

If we look at fine metalwork from Scotland, we can see that several items, torcs included, which have a known, and very discrete, origin in Scotland have been found in the south, even in the torc heartland of East Anglia. So could this be happening with torus torcs, also?

If we look at the Newark and Netherurd torcs (here turned into a complete torc so people have a chance to admire how magnificent it must have once been) we know that these two torcs were [made or finished by the same hand](#) and yet were found some 200 miles apart. Despite the fact that the Newark torc may have been [moved from its original place of deposition](#) there is no suggestion that either torc came from the south.

In addition, the identification of a further torc from Hoard H at Snettisham, which shows similar motifs to those seen in the Newark and Netherurd terminals, appears to have been made or finished by the

same hand. As such, this could suggest the H.7 Snettisham torc is an import to East Anglia, rather than an indigenous southern example.

I now want to look at four case studies, where craft insights have altered the standard theories about torcs.

Case study 1: Concentric circles must be cast.

This idea, although not published, has been discussed with me on several occasions as further evidence that torus torcs must be cast.

However, replication work by the late Ford Hallam clearly shows this not to be the case.

In addition, the creation of concentric circles using a non-Western, exterior working technique, has shown that the reliance on Western working techniques and terminologies is not to be advised.

Non-Western gold working techniques.

Exterior

Netherurd *Snettisham Great torc* *Ford's circles*

Interior

Netherurd *Ford's circles*

The *uchidashi* 打ち出し (trans. 'hammering down'/'hammer reveal') technique is used to make a three-dimensional relief from a flat sheet of metal. Unlike repoussage - which works from the interior - it involves a hammer and punch forming the metal from the front side, defining a form in a way that retains the thickness.

Concentric circles in torus torcs aren't cast, or made using repoussage.

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Ford's replication also showed that the evidence of working seen on the interior of the Netherurd terminal best matches that produced by the use of the *uchidashi* technique. This interior evidence can also be seen on the [Clevedon](#) and [Near Stowmarket](#) torc terminals.

Case study 2: The Clevedon terminal.

The Clevedon terminal has long been cited as an example showing the longevity of 'Celtic art' styles.

Case study 2: the Clevedon torc terminal

*'Faith in the chronological significance...of the stylistic sequence has long been undermined by pieces like the Clevedon torc'**

Decorated on the collar with Stead's early Stage 1/2 scrolls (left), but with a more typically late, Stage V, triskele on the face (right)...

...explained as longevity of art styles in the later Iron Age.

*Perspectives on insular La Tène art', Macdonald 2007, 332 Image © Trustees of the British Museum

However, an examination of the Clevedon terminal has suggested an alternative explanation:

But... what if the terminal is not all one date, and has been re-modelled at a later date?

> Could torus torcs be earlier than previously thought?

This would suggest that the Clevedon terminal was originally the collar of a torus torc similar to the Netherurd and Snettisham Great torc, which was cut down and reworked at a later date. This explains the earlier and later art styles as [being representative of an earlier and later working and re-working of the torc](#). Such evidence adds to a growing corpus of torcs which have been re-worked and re-modelled over time. One such torc that this may also apply to is the Snettisham Great torc.

Case study 3: The Snettisham Great torc.

In the recently published Snettisham volumes, [there are a number of issues that I have identified which point to a lack of understanding of the goldsmithing process](#). The Great torc, in particular, is described as being of a composite sheet/cast hybrid construction, with a sheet/hammered core and cast torus shell.

However, there is little evidence for this assumption, with typical features of a sheet terminal construction being present on the torc.

Case study 3: the Snettisham Great torc

'This evidence suggests that the toroidal terminals of the Great Torc were originally formed as open castings ... with all the deep three-dimensional decorative design elements being cast to shape with the metal of the terminal.'

Meeks *et al*, Technology and Manufacture of the Snettisham Torcs, 2024

In addition, the thickness of the terminal alloy, at only 0.3mm to 0.6mm is well below that which could be cast, even using modern methods.

Talking to craftspeople...

<p><i>Confirmed sheet torcs thicknesses:</i></p> <p>Grotesque torc terminal: c.0.4-0.6mm Netherurd torc terminal: c.0.5-0.7mm Near Stowmarket terminal: c.0.6-0.8mm</p>	<p><i>Confirmed cast/hybrid torcs thicknesses:</i></p> <p>Sedgeford torc terminal thickness: c.1-2mm Newark torc terminal thickness: c.1-2mm</p>
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Great torc terminal thickness: 0.3-0.6mm

"It's hard to cast under c.1mm even with modern equipment and materials, all the more so with extensive areas of flat sheet. I'm talking about top quality investment materials such as phosphate-based investments with electronic centrifuge under vacuum and ideal temperatures... I speak from experience of over 20,000 castings in over fifty years of working in the craft."

"My immediate thought was "that's not possible to cast", and the numbers above, well, 1.2mm or 18ga is about the thinnest I'd feel comfortable with casting, but of course with vacuum or centrifugal assist."

"I've cast things 0.5mm but they've been small, with nowhere near the kind of detail. No way that's cast."

"I'd like to see someone try to cast gold that thin especially for something that big and complicated."

The interpretation of a cast terminal shell appears to originate from the finding of a small casting defect in the shell of one of the terminals. However, an understanding of the alloy working process, where a casting porosity can transfer to a sheet artefact does not appear to have been recognised. As such, there is no evidence that the Snettisham Great torc is cast, but much to suggest it is made from sheet/hammered gold alloy.

*"Oh God, I hate it when that happens: you're hammering away and suddenly the flaw appears. B*gger all you can do about it either!"*

Figure 17.91a-b a) Great Torc terminal with the location of the casting defect on the side of the torus in the centre of the marked square (image width c. 35mm); b) Close-up of the same dendritic cold-shut casting defect. The solidity within the defect shows that it is not a crack from sheet-metalworking (x100. Note that the close-up image is rotated c. 90 degrees with respect to (a). Scale 200 µm (0.2mm), image width 2.5mm)

Meeks et al, Technology and Manufacture of the Snettisham Torcs, 2024

The understanding that the Snettisham Great torc is made from sheet/hammered gold along with a close examination of the manufacture, decoration - and faults - of this torc opens up [an alternative biography](#).

In this scenario, the terminals appear to have been made by two different makers, using differing quality gold alloys, and decorating each torc in an identifiably unique way.

Struggling with gold: an alternative Great torc biography...

The big problems are all in Terminal 2. Terminal 1 is pretty much perfect.

The gold alloy used/ability to control heat/ability of the goldsmith in Terminal 2 did not allow for a good finish... but it is sheet gold.

> Are Terminals 1 and 2 of the same date of manufacture? Made by the same person?

This chimes with the evidence of the Clevedon terminal - which appears to have been repurposed as a new buffer torc terminal - and of the Netherurd terminal, which has been carefully removed from its neck ring (dents on the terminal end show that it was once attached to one) and which was perhaps previously intended to have a new neck ring and terminal as part of a reworked torus torc?

Case study 4: Hoard L from Snettisham.

My final few slides are about how a craft perspective can perhaps give us, more widely, an alternative view on the Snettisham material, using the Hoard L torc deposit as an example. Hoard L comprises twenty-one torcs buried in two deposits (the first torcs L.1-L.7, the second torcs L.8-L.21) separated by a small soil horizon, but apparently within the same larger pit.

The torcs are shown below, in order of deposition, with L.1 at the top, and L.21 at the bottom. The famous Grottesque torc, L.19, was the third torc added to the lower deposit.

I have colour-coded the torcs by dominant metal in each alloy, with blue for silver, rust for copper alloy and yellow for gold alloys, with a darker yellow signifying a richer gold alloy than that seen in the lighter yellow colour-coded examples. This follows the alloys identified in the Snettisham volumes (Farley & Joy 2024, Fig. 23.5). I have also identified if the torc terminals are cast, sheet, decorated, gilded and/or hollow and have given each torc a simplified number of processes used to make each torc: cast terminals, hammered wire terminals, the making of the wire neck-ring and decorating each count as a single process.

The manufacture of separate sheet (and some of the hammered wire) terminals involves multiple processes of manufacture and soldering/bonding, etc, so these terminals are classed as items that involve more than one (1+) process to make. Although not precise, this classification allows a general grouping of the torcs, according to whether they use two, three or more than three manufacturing processes.

As can be seen above, in general, torcs with more complicated manufacturing processes cluster towards the base of the hoard, with less complicated torcs found in the upper levels. However, please note the top, and final, torc in the deposit, L.1, has a more complicated manufacturing method if compared to those others in the upper deposit.

It can also be seen that torcs with hollow terminals, whether cast or sheet made, concentrate in the lower part of the hoard. Again note torc L.1, the only hollow terminal torc in the upper levels.

Sheet torcs are only to be found in the lower level of the hoard, although torc L.21, the first deposited torc in the hoard, is cast. Torcs not identified in the list as cast or sheet, have hammered wire or overcast wire terminals.

Gilded torcs, in this case mercury gilded copper alloy, are only to be found in the upper levels of the hoard as a whole, although interestingly, they can be found both in the upper, and lower, separated deposits.

Current knowledge would suggest that the common use of silver and gilding only starts in these islands from around the 2nd to 1st centuries BCE. We also have a radiocarbon date for torc L.6, which would fit within this parameter. Additionally, the 'Plastic' art style of the Grotesque torc (torc L.19) would suggest a possible 3rd century date for this torc, at the lower level of the hoard.

My [previous work](#) has suggested that there may be a transition from sheet to cast working, with cast 'copies' being made of 'original' sheet/hammered torcs. This would seem to fit with the Hoard L finds, with sheet torcs only being found in the lower levels of the hoard. As such, taken as a whole, by looking at alloy type, manufacturing process, radiocarbon and art historical dating evidence it would appear that those torcs at the base of the entire hoard could be seen to be older than those in the upper levels.

However, this assumption does not necessarily apply to torcs L.1 and L.21 which appear out of place in this sequence. Although this oddity has been recognised by Farley & Joy for torc L.1, and the upper torcs of several other Snettisham hoards (Farley & Joy 2024, 592), the possible addition of torc L.21 as an 'out of place' example might suggest that the torcs in the bottom AND top of each hoard were of particular significance.

This analysis would also suggest that the hoards, irrelevant of the number of deposits in each pit, should be looked at very much as a whole. The red horizontal line separating the upper and lower deposits of Hoard H (see above), does not seem to have relevance to the deposition pattern of the torcs within the hoard as a whole, with upper torcs of the lower deposit fitting in well with those of the – albeit soil-separated - deposit above.

It would also suggest that, top and bottom torcs perhaps excluded, within the bulk of each hoard, older torcs were placed at the bottom, with successively younger torcs placed on top. As such, by looking at where they appear in the deposition sequence, it may be possible to date these torcs much more accurately than we can at present. Should we maybe be looking at each torc as representing a generation of around 20-30 years? Could each torc then have been linked to a specific person, or familial/group generation?

It would also suggest that we should be perhaps looking at the Snettisham hoards as buried lineages or ancestries: the long curated/collected/looked after symbols/status items of perhaps a community, family or group that were buried in one episode after their use above ground was no longer deemed necessary or required. This idea fits with the [previous work I have carried out on the Grotesque torc.](#)

The above is very much a work in progress, but the patterns identified above also seem to apply to several of the other Snettisham hoards - these hoards (top and bottom torcs excepted) seem to grade from sheet/hammered, decorated and more complicated gold torcs in their lower levels through to less complicated silver/copper alloy and gilded examples in their upper.

